

Method for Estimating Effective Elastic Moduli of Dispersely Reinforced Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

To estimate overall elastic properties of composite materials, the cell model methods are made use of, which are simple but very efficient in treating various problems of disperse media. Composite materials reinforced by continuous parallel fibers are mainly considered. One of the effective elastic moduli is, in particular, estimated by applying the scheme of the self-consistent cell model.

INTRODUCTION

It is the aim of the present paper to estimate theoretically the effective elastic moduli of dispersely reinforced composite materials. The local field in such materials must be very complicated as a result of many-body interaction. For engineering purposes, however, it is enough in many cases to know the overall relationship between the large scale strain and stress, which is expressed by using the effective elastic coefficients. In the case of transversally isotropic composite materials under consideration there are five effective elastic constants. Many works have been done theoretically to eliminate these coefficients in terms of physical properties and compositions of constituent materials (1-7). In the present paper the author proposes the cell model method for the analysis (8-10), which gives, remarkably improved estimate in contrast to its simplicity. As the example, composite materials reinforced by continuous parallel fibers will be considered. In the case of such transversally isotropic materials there are five effective elastic coefficients to be estimated.

PLANE DEFORMATION

Plane deformation problems will be mainly considered in this paper, where the displacement takes place in the plane perpendicular to the parallel continuous fibers. In this case two effective elastic constants out of five make appearance, one of which is obtained easily by using the simple cell model and the other will need to make use of a little sophisticated scheme, i.e., the self-consistent cell model (Fig.1).

Let the coordinates of a point in the plane of displacement be x_i ($i=1,2$). The infinitesimal displacement is denoted by u_i , the strain by ϵ_{ij} , and the stress by σ_{ij} . Since elasticity is isotropic in this plane for the constituent

materials as well as the composite material on the average, the stress-strain relation is generally given by the following form:

$$\sigma_{ij} = 2M \epsilon_{ij} + (K-M) \epsilon \delta_{ij} \quad (\epsilon \equiv \epsilon_{kk}), \quad (1)$$

where K and M are the elastic constants and δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta. The summation convention has been applied to a pair of repeated indices. The strain is related to the displacement by

$$\epsilon_{ij} = (\partial_i u_j + \partial_j u_i)/2 \quad (\partial_i \equiv \partial / \partial x_i). \quad (2)$$

The equation of equilibrium is given by $\partial_k \sigma_{ki} = 0$, i.e.,

$$M \Delta u_i + K \partial_i \epsilon = 0 \quad (\epsilon \equiv \partial_k u_k), \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta \equiv \partial_k \partial_k$ is the Laplacian operator in two-dimensional problems.

Let the representative deformation be X_{ij} ($= X_{ji}$), which is divided into two components:

$$X_{ij} = X \delta_{ij} + \hat{X}_{ij} \quad (X \equiv X_{kk}/3, \hat{X}_{kk} = 0), \quad (4)$$

where $3X$ is the dilatation and \hat{X}_{ij} is the deviatoric strain. In linear problems, the local displacement is proportional to X_{ij} , and further in isotropic cases the displacement is a linear sum of two independent ones, due to X and X_{ij} separately. In the case of the representative dilation $3X$, the displacement takes a general form

$$u_i = \frac{1}{2} h(r) x_i X \quad (r \equiv \sqrt{x_k x_k}). \quad (5)$$

The solution to (3) reads

$$h(r) = A + B (a/r)^2, \quad (6)$$

where A and B are the integration constants, a being representative length. The stress σ_{ri} on a surface $r = \text{const.}$ is given by

$$\sigma_{ri} = [AK - B (a/r)^2 M] (x_i/r) X. \quad (7)$$

For the representative traceless deformation \hat{X}_{ij} , the form of displacement is given by

$$u_i = [f(r) \delta_{ij} + g(r) x_i x_j] x_k \hat{X}_{jk}. \quad (8)$$

The solution to (3) gives

$$\begin{aligned} f(r) &= A + B (r/a)^2 + C (a/r)^2 + D (a/r)^4, \\ r^2 g(r) &= -\frac{K+2M}{2K+M} B \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^2 + \frac{K}{M} C \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^2 - 2D \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^4, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where A , B , C and D are new integration constants. The stress on a surface $r = \text{const.}$ is given in this case by

$$\sigma_{ri} = 2M [f_O(r) \delta_{ij} + g_O(r) x_i x_j] x_k \hat{X}_{jk} / r, \quad (10)$$

where

$$f_O(r) = A + \frac{3K}{2K+M} B \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^2 + \frac{K}{M} C \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^2 - 3D \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^4,$$

$$r^2 g_{ij}(r) = - \frac{3K}{2K+M} B \left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^2 - \frac{3K}{M} C \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^2 + 6D \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^4. \quad (11)$$

SIMPLE CELL MODEL FOR DETERMINING \bar{K}

Although the average deformation is uniform over the whole region, the local field may be complicated from the many-body interaction. It is understood, however, that the field is a repetition of the pattern around a fiber. Consequently, it will suffice to solve the field over some space around a single fiber. This basic region around a fiber will be called a cell. The shape of the cell be assumed to be circular because of randomness of location and orientation, if any, of fibers. Let the equivalent radius of fibers be a . The boundary surface of the cell is concentrically circular, the radius of which is let b . The size of the cell, i.e., b can be determined as follows. Let n fibers be dispersed in a unit area, so that the area allotted to a cell is $1/n$ on the average. This area can be assumed to be that of the cell. The radius b is, therefore, calculated from the relation $\pi b^2 = 1/n$. The volume fraction of the dispersed phase is denoted by z , where $z = n\pi a^2$. thus, we have

$$b = (1/\pi n)^{1/2}, \quad z = (a/b)^2, \quad z' = 1 - (a/b)^2, \quad (12)$$

where $z'=1-z$ is the volume fraction of the continuous phase. Henceforth, quantities of the matrix phase are distinguished by attaching a prime ' and quantities of the composite material by superposing a bar -, whereas those of the fiber phase are without mark.

To calculate the effective elastic constant \bar{K} , we shall apply the method of the simple cell model, where the field outside the cell is assumed to be for that for the uniform average deformation X . Hence, $\bar{u}_i = (1/2) x_i X$ for $r \geq b$, so that $\bar{A} = 1$ and $\bar{B} = 0$ in (5). The structure of the cell is such that the region $0 \leq r \leq a$ is of fiber phase and the region $a \leq r \leq b$ of matrix phase. The boundary and interface conditions are as follows: u_i and σ_{rj} are finite at $r=0$ and continuous at $r=a$ and b . These conditions determine the unknown constants A, B, A', B' and the wanted elastic constant \bar{K} ,

$$A = (K'+M')/[(K'+M')z + (K+M')z'], \quad B = 0, \\ A' = A (K+M')/(K'+M'), \quad B' = -A (K-K')/(K'+M'), \quad (13)$$

and

$$\bar{K} = [K(K'+M')z + K(K+M')z']/[(K'+M')z + (K+M')z'], \quad (14)$$

The last relation coincides with Hill's formula.

THE SELF-CONSISTENT CELL MODEL FOR DETERMINING \bar{M}

To determine the effective rigidity \bar{M} the expressions of the types of (8) and (10) will be employed. The application of the simple model is compressible, since the number of the boundary conditions exceeds that of unknowns. To overcome the difficulty we shall assume that outside the cell there extends a continuous material of elasticity \bar{K} and \bar{M} , the last of which is not known yet. This scheme will be called the self-consistent cell model in the present paper. An important condition will be given as follows:

$$\bar{\bar{T}} + r^2 \bar{\bar{g}}/2 = 1 + O(a^2/r^2) \quad \text{as } r \rightarrow \infty, \quad (15)$$

which comes from requiring that $\hat{\bar{\epsilon}}_{ij}$ is equal to the volume average of the strain ϵ_{ij} over the entire region with sufficient strctness

$$\lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} \left[\int_{0 \leq r \leq a} \partial_i u_j \, dv + \int_{a \leq r \leq b} \partial_i u_j' \, dv' + \int_{b \leq r \leq R} \partial_i \bar{u}_j \, d\bar{v} \right] / \pi R^2 = \hat{\bar{\epsilon}}_{ij}.$$

From (15) it follows that $\bar{A}=1$, $\bar{B}=0$, $\bar{C}=0$. Thus the determining equations are given as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A' + B' + C' + D' &= A + B, \\
 -\frac{K'+2M'}{2K'+M'} B' + \frac{K'}{M'} C' - 2D' &= -\frac{K+2M}{2K+M} B, \\
 A' + \frac{3K'}{2K'+M'} B' + \frac{K'}{M'} C' - 3D' &= \frac{M}{M'} \left(A + \frac{3K}{2K+M} B \right), \\
 -\frac{3K'}{2K'+M'} B' - \frac{3K'}{M'} C' + 6D' &= -\frac{M}{M'} \frac{3K}{2K+M} B, \\
 A' + B'/z + C'z + D'z^2 &= 1 + \bar{D}z^2, \\
 -\frac{K'+2M'}{2K'+M'} B'z^{-1} + \frac{K'}{M'} C'z - 2D'z^2 &= -2\bar{D}z^2, \\
 A' + \frac{3K'}{2K'+M'} B'z^{-1} + \frac{K'}{M'} C'z - 3D'z^2 &= \frac{\bar{M}}{M'} (1 - 3\bar{D}z^2), \\
 -\frac{3K'}{2K'+M'} B'z^{-1} - \frac{3K'}{M'} C'z + 6D'z^2 &= -\frac{\bar{M}}{M'} 6\bar{D}z^2.
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

The unknowns are A , B , A' , B' , C' , D' , \bar{D} and \bar{M}/M' , the last of which is obtained like an eigenvalue.

THE OTHER EFFECTIVE ELASTIC COEFFICIENTS

In the case of the composite material with transversally isotropic symmetry, the three-dimensional stress-strain relation is expressed by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{\sigma}_{ij} &= 2\bar{M} \bar{\epsilon}_{ij} + [(\bar{K}-\bar{M}) \bar{\epsilon} + \bar{L} \bar{\epsilon}_{zz}] \delta_{ij}, \\
 \bar{\sigma}_{iz} &= 2\bar{G} \bar{\epsilon}_{iz}, \quad \bar{\sigma}_{zz} = \bar{N} \bar{\epsilon}_{zz} + \bar{L} \bar{\epsilon},
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

where $i, j = 1, 2, z$ is the component along the fiber-axis, and $\bar{\epsilon}_{zz} = \partial \bar{u} / \partial z$, $\bar{\epsilon}_{iz} = (\partial_i \bar{u}_z + \partial_z \bar{u}_i) / 2$. The coefficients \bar{G} , \bar{L} and \bar{N} can be determined by making use of the simple cell method, obtaining

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{G} &= M' [2Mz + (M+M')z'] / [2M'z + (M+M')z'], \\
 \bar{L} &= [(K-M)(K'+M')z + (K'-M')(K+M')z'] / P, \\
 \bar{N} &= (K+M)z + (K'+M')z' - zz'(K-M-K'+M')^2 / P, \\
 P &\equiv (K'+M')z + (K+M)z',
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

which coincide with Hill's results.

Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios are also defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{E}_{ij} &= \frac{1}{E_1} [(1+\bar{\nu}_1) \bar{\sigma}_{ij} - \bar{\nu}_1 \bar{\sigma}] - \frac{\bar{\nu}_2}{E_2} \sigma_{zz}, \\
 \bar{E}_{zz} &= \frac{1}{E_2} (\bar{\sigma}_{zz} - \bar{\nu}_2 \bar{\sigma}), \quad \bar{\sigma} \equiv \sigma_{kk}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

There are the following relations between the coefficients in (18) and those in (17):

$$\bar{E}_1 = 4\bar{M} \frac{\bar{K}\bar{N} - \bar{L}^2}{(K+M)\bar{N} - \bar{L}^2}, \quad \bar{E}_2 = \bar{N} - \frac{\bar{L}^2}{K}, \tag{20}$$

$$\bar{v}_1 = \frac{(\bar{K}-\bar{M})\bar{N} - \bar{L}^2}{(\bar{K}+\bar{M})\bar{N} - \bar{L}^2}, \quad \bar{v}_2 = \frac{\bar{L}}{2\bar{K}}.$$

NUMERICAL CALCULATIONS AND CONCLUSION

The effective rigidity \bar{M} is determined by numerically solving (16) obtained by the scheme of the self-consistent cell model. J. J. Hermans obtained the following formula (6):

$$\frac{\bar{M}}{M} = \frac{2zM(K'+M') + 2z'MM' + z'K'(M+M')}{2zM'(K'+M') + 2z'MM' + z'K'(M+M')} \quad (21)$$

The numerical results by the present method and those by Hermans' formula are composed in Fig.2, where $E = 10.6 \times 10^6$ psi, $\nu = 0.22$ for glass fiber and $E' = 0.5 \times 10^6$ psi, $\nu' = 0.35$ for epoxy resin matrix. The empirical points in Fig.2 are from Hermans' paper. It is seen that the method of the self-consistent gives a certain improvement.

Stresses on the surface of fiber can be calculated after solving (16), which are shown in Fig.3, where $\bar{\sigma}_{rt}$ is the apparent stress and equal to $2Mx_k \hat{X}_{ik} / a \sqrt{x_k} = a$. The second index r means the radial component, while t does k the tangential component.

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Fig.1 A self-consistent cell model.

Fig.2 The effective Young's modulus E_1 vs. the volume fraction of fibers z .

Fig.3 Stress on the fiber surface vs. the volume fraction of fibers.